

The Pedagogy of Death and the pandemic. Leading educationalist' views

Pedagogía de la Muerte y pandemia. Reflexiones de científicos de referencia en Ciencias de la Educación

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Abstract

The recent COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a worldwide increase in fatalities and the overall visibility of death. Some academic disciplines have redefined their principles and paradigms in the wake of this crisis. This study enquires into whether pedagogy has made any changes in the area of education on death as a result of the pandemic experience. Thirteen leading Spanish academics from the education field, chosen according to their number of citations in *Web of Science*, were interviewed. A qualitative phenomenographic design was adopted, using scripted semi-structured interviews centred on participants' views. The main conclusions were: (1) the pandemic had caused participants to make reflections that might lead to an enhanced awareness of the educational value of death and finitude; (2) their relationships with their students had become closer, gaining in understanding and empathy, and thus fostering more compassionate educational spaces; (3) participants had made no significant changes in their teaching or research in relation to death; and (4) they highlighted the importance for education of treating death as a normal topic and including it in school curricula. These findings indicate the need to provide opportunities to analyse the impact of the pandemic on pedagogy in the area of radical issues such as death, and with regard to developing education policies aimed at systematically including death in education.

Keywords: Pedagogy of Death; pandemic; education sciences; university faculty; educational change.

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Resumen

En los últimos años, la pandemia causada por la COVID-19 ha incrementado la presencia de la muerte y los fallecimientos a nivel mundial. Algunas disciplinas científicas han redefinido sus principios y paradigmas a raíz de la pandemia. Esta investigación aborda los posibles cambios en la Pedagogía, en relación con la pertinencia de una educación que incluya la muerte desde la experiencia de la pandemia. En el estudio se entrevista a trece académicos de referencia en España en Ciencias de la Educación seleccionados por el número de citas recibidas en *Web of Science*. Se opta por un diseño cualitativo de tipo fenomenográfico, centrado en las perspectivas de los participantes, creando un guion para las entrevistas semiestructuradas. Las conclusiones principales son: (1) la pandemia ha generado en los participantes algunas reflexiones que pueden sustentar una mayor conciencia de educatividad de la muerte y la finitud; (2) la relación con los estudiantes universitarios se ha intensificado, en términos de comprensión y empatía, promoviendo espacios educativos más compasivos; (3) no se aprecian cambios relevantes en la docencia y la investigación en relación con la muerte en los académicos participantes; y (4) los participantes destacan la importancia para la educación de que la muerte se trate con normalidad y perspectiva curricular en las etapas escolares. La investigación tiene implicaciones como la necesidad de promover espacios reflexivos sobre el impacto de la pandemia en la Pedagogía y, concretamente, en temas radicales como la muerte, o en la definición de políticas educativas que normalicen la muerte como elemento formativo.

Palabras clave: Pedagogía de la Muerte; pandemia; Ciencias de la Educación; profesores universitarios; cambio educativo.

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had a global impact, affecting both the individual and family lives of millions of people. Declared by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11th March 2020, the pandemic increased the visibility of death in society and, consequently, in our schools. The period of the pandemic, then, can be considered one of the greatest shocks for humanity in the last century. These exceptional circumstances have led to the redefinition of academic disciplines (Cárdenas-González and Álvarez-Buylla, 2020) and given rise to numerous studies identifying shifts in the paradigms and centres of interest of fields such as economics (Mahi et al., 2021), psychology (Ağirkan, 2023) and law (Murdie, 2022). We can also reflect on pedagogy as a fundamental science that studies education—following the Central European and Latin tradition, which distinguishes the discipline, i.e., pedagogy itself, from the field of application, i.e., education (Herrán et al., 2024). Thus, the experience of the pandemic may have prompted a reassessment of education and the figure of the educator (Hill et al., 2020).

While initially education studies were oriented towards problem-solving, for example in technological adaptation and online teaching (Amaya et al., 2024), the current period, with a more distanced and rational view of the worst months of the pandemic, can contribute to a deeper understanding of the pedagogical foundations underpinning educational action by identifying gaps and contradictions in our current educational model. One such gap is teaching that exploits the educational potential of death, a topic that is not normally addressed in the curricula of the countries where research has been conducted (Herrán et al., 2019; Paul et al., 2023; Rodríguez et al., 2022a; Sonbul and Çelik, 2023), despite the fact that the educational community recognizes its pedagogical value (Rodríguez et al., 2022b; Rodríguez et al., 2024; Serrano et al., 2024).

Since we find ourselves in a particularly interesting period for rethinking educational issues, this article set out to ascertain the opinion of leading Spanish education sciences scholars on the potential relevance of the Pedagogy of Death in the wake of the pandemic.

1.1. The pandemic and its impact on education

In their article “Preparing educators for the time of COVID... and beyond”, Darling-Hammond and Hylter (2020) made the following observation: “While learning in the time of COVID has been challenging for students and prospective teachers alike, this moment of disruption has created the opportunity for rethinking and reinventing preparation, as well as schooling itself” (p. 463). Several years later, with the worst of the pandemic over, Assunção and Craig (2023) raised the possibility of reimagining teacher education in the wake of the pandemic: “The aftermath of the pandemic may be a time to rethink the purpose of teacher education and its role in transforming education” (p. 785). According to these and other scholars, the pandemic and the reflections it has given rise to are likely to bring about shifts in concepts and paradigms in pedagogy and education, as has happened in the other fields mentioned above. In this regard, Hudak (2023) characterizes COVID-19 and its effects on humanity as a transformative event in redefining the essence of education.

The pandemic, therefore, may have caused profound changes in our understanding of education, involving advances in both methodology and teaching resources, especially in terms of online teaching, which was largely retained once face-to-face classroom teaching had been resumed (Sharma and Saini, 2023). Ibáñez-Martín and Ahedo (2023) point to four significant issues arising from the pandemic which have implications for the purposes of education: (1) we should bear in mind that there can be no authentic education without reflection on the meaning of life; (2) vulnerability is a condition characterizing all human beings; (3) the pandemic revealed our deep dependence on nature; and (4) the pandemic highlighted the negative consequences of the individualism that pervades contemporary society.

As Ibáñez-Martín and Ahedo (2023) argue, the awareness of human vulnerability, and therefore our relationship with our own death and that of others, can help us rethink the principles and purposes of education and ask ourselves what its key subject matter should be: for example death, due to its radical nature for humanity (Herrán *et al.*, 2019).

1.2. The Pedagogy of Death and the pandemic

The relationship between death and education has been addressed through the approaches of two different epistemological traditions (Herrán *et al.*, 2024). In English-speaking countries, it has been explored and analysed in the field of death education, which studies the teaching of death-related topics in the social, healthcare and education fields. In the Central European and Latin tradition, on the other hand, a distinction is made between the Pedagogy of Death, which is the discipline of study, and its field of application, i.e. education that encompasses death. The Pedagogy of Death is seen as the scientific field that studies the inclusion of death in education for a more conscious life (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2022a). Therefore, in accordance with the objective of this article, this study adopts the Pedagogy of Death approach.

From studies into the inclusion of death in curricula conducted in countries such as Spain (Herrán *et al.*, 2019; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2022a), Turkey (Sonbul and Çelik, 2023) and Scotland (Paul *et al.*, 2023), we can deduce that death is not normally or intentionally addressed in teaching. Education systems underwent the pandemic without having envisaged an education that would foster an awareness of death, either by preparing students to deal with it by addressing it in the curriculum, or through educational support for bereavement (Herrán *et al.*, 2019). Students, teachers and administrative staff in schools returned to the classroom while still living under the shadow of death in their immediate surroundings and

the media (Smilie, 2022). Rarely has death hit schools around the world so hard, with the pandemic providing an opportunity to realise the value of an education that encompasses death (Herrán, 2020).

Despite this urgent natural and social situation, the Pedagogy of Death and its relationship to the pandemic have not been subjects of significant scientific interest, compared to studies on virtual teaching, communication technologies and mental health in the education community. In higher education, some studies have assessed the effects of death education programs on reducing anxiety around death (Weisskirch and Crossman, 2022). In schools, addressing death in the curriculum could respond to death-related concerns and anxieties in the wake of the pandemic and, from a broader perspective, contribute to a more comprehensive and humanistic education.

Since this study adopts the perspective of the Pedagogy of Death, i.e. the scientific discipline that studies the inclusion of death in education (Rodríguez et al., 2022a), we set out to ascertain the views of leading Spanish education scholars on the relevance of education that encompasses death, and its implications for improving education in the wake of the pandemic.

2. Method

In order to address the research objective, a qualitative phenomenographic design was chosen (Murillo et al., 2022), an approach that assumes that significant knowledge can be found in participants' views and perspectives (Marshall and Rossman, 2016). The relevance of this study design stems from its focus on exploring the varying ways in which participants understand the phenomena studied (Murillo et al., 2022). In this case, the aim was to determine, from both present and retrospective standpoints (Bolívar et al., 2001), how participants were influenced by their personal and professional experiences with respect to the object of study, i.e., the relationship of the Pedagogy of Death to the pandemic and the improvement of education.

This qualitative phenomenographic design, then, seeks to deepen our understanding of the phenomena studied (Krause, 1995). It is an effective approach to the problem when the aim is to examine the way in which people perceive and experience the phenomena under investigation, through exploring their interpretations, points of view and the meanings they assign to events (Lichtman, 2013; Punch, 2014). The phenomenographic design thus orients researchers towards participants' subjective experiences and meaning construction. It is suitable to this study, since, rather than seeking generalizable results, here we set out to investigate the views of leading educationalists and their pedagogical implications regarding the emerging field of the Pedagogy of Death in relation to the recent pandemic.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the coordinating university. The research team that carried out both the interviews and the data analysis consisted of four researchers.

2.1. Participants

The study population consisted of tenured teaching and research staff (professors and tenured lecturers) from education faculties at Spanish universities with a high number of citations in journals indexed in the databases *Education and Educational Research*, *Education*, *Scientific Disciplines*, and *Education, Special, Web of Science (WoS)*. The purpose of choosing this specific group was to garner the views of leading Spanish scholars in the education field. Although currently the debate around how scholarly work should be assessed acknowledges that academic success cannot be reduced to the number of publications and citations registered in these international databases, for the purposes of this study it was chosen to employ clear, objective inclusion criteria, whilst accepting any limitations that this may have on sample selection. A complementary further criterion,

ensuring better selection of participants, was the choice of academics in the highest positions (professors and tenured lecturers).

The sampling was random, using a list of scholars ranked according to their number of publications in WoS from 2012 to 2022. A list of 170 educationalists meeting the criteria was drawn up, the highest-scoring with 63 citations and the lowest eighteen. The research team sent invitations in batches of ten until a sample of thirteen lecturers and professors was reached. The final number of interviewees was justified by saturation in the data analysis and the recommended phenomenographic research sample size of close to fifteen (Murillo et al., 2022). A total of 132 scholars were invited, with 119 declining or not responding to the invitation (an acceptance rate of almost 10%).

The final sample of thirteen scholars comprised eight women and five men. Five were professors and eight senior lecturers. Seven were from the area of Didactics and School Organization, three from Specific Didactics, one from Education Research Methodology and Analysis, and one from Evolutionary and Educational Psychology. Scholars from eight regions of Spain took part. Participants are identified in the data analysis with the letter *P* for participant followed by an identification number (1 to 13).

2.2. Research technique and instrument

The study was conducted through semi-structured phenomenographic interviews. An ad hoc script of twenty questions was drawn up, based on the theory and prior studies discussed in the introduction to this article, and divided into four parts: (1) demographic data on participants' research and teaching; (2) an introductory section with questions on personal experience of the pandemic; (3) an exploratory part with questions on the Pedagogy of Death and the pandemic; and (4) a closing section featuring questions on the conclusions of the interview. An example of a question from the introductory part is: "Do you know if any of your students lost loved ones during the pandemic? How did you find out and, if you did, what did you do?" In the exploratory section, questions such as the following were asked: "Do you think that if death were a normal educational topic, the reaction to the pandemic would have been different? Why?" Lastly, an example of a question in the closing section is: "Has this interview led to any changes/reflection/learning? If so, can you specify?" Validation was carried out by four experts in the Pedagogy of Death with more than five years' research experience in the field each, and through a pilot study with two participants who met the criteria for the sample. This resulted in some questions being omitted and others reformulated for the final script. The interviews, with an average duration of 45 minutes, were conducted from March to July 2023, and were carried out online, since interviewees were based in different regions of Spain.

2.3. Data analysis

Once the interviews had been conducted, they were transcribed and imported into the NVivo 14 program, which was used to perform the content analysis. The rationale behind the data analysis was based on a complementary twofold approach. On the one hand it was deductive, starting from the pre-established topics and questions in the script (while also being open to the emergence of other topics and questions in the course of the interview, given its semi-structured nature) and based on existing theory and knowledge about the Pedagogy of Death. On the other hand it was also inductive, since the main categories were created through ongoing analysis of the data, redefining some initial questions as a result of the experience gained in the interviews, and saturating the information through the thirteen interviews. In accordance with the phenomenographic approach (Murillo et al., 2022), the analysis was performed while new data was still being collected, thereby leading to saturation once no substantially different meanings appeared in relation to the research objective. The units of meaning that gave rise to the final categories corresponded to the core areas of study, and taken as a whole provided

answers to the central research questions. Finally, triangulation was addressed through the participation of the whole research team in analysing every interview.

3. Results

Before discussing the data and its organization into the categories and subcategories that emerged during the interpretation of participants' testimonies, we present the terms they used most frequently. These indicate, firstly, the importance of the topics covered in the interviews and, secondly, the direction of participants' discourses. Thus the most-used terms were "pandemic" (n = 259), "death" (n = 164) and "university" (n = 99), as we would expect, given the topic and the setting. Also there appeared other terms enabling an initial approach to the focus of participants' discourse. These included "meaning" (n = 80), "teaching" (n = 73), "staff" (n = 70), "students" (n = 64) and "changes" (n = 62).

The initial categories were based on the three areas mentioned above (introduction, exploration and closure), and refined during the data analysis into the following definitive classification: (a) experiences during the pandemic; (b) changes in teaching and research around death as a result of the pandemic; and (c) the relevance of the Pedagogy of Death in the light of the pandemic. The results in these categories and, where applicable, in related subcategories, are presented below.

3.1. Experiences during the pandemic

This category groups together the responses from the first interview questions, referring to personal and professional experience during the pandemic.

With regard to its impact on participants' personal lives, some comments mentioned the difficulty of the period, partly due to its association with loss and death. For example, P1 remarked that the pandemic "was tough, a really tough experience". Another participant (P2) talked about the difficulties faced by students during the pandemic: "I remember the effect the state my students were in had on me." However, in contrast to the sometimes frenetic pace of today's society, some participants also referred to the opportunities presented by the lockdown: "For me, it was a gift, and one that I'll always remember. I never felt disconnected from anything or anyone, and I really cherished the silence, the peace, and being able to slow down, read and think about what I'd read, reflect, meditate, write" (P3). In the same vein, P4 commented that "It was a very productive time for research". Participants commented not only on opportunities to devote more time to certain aspects of their work, such as research, but also to others relating to well-being and personal development. For example, one participant (P3) described the time as an "encounter with myself"; while another explained, "[I've] become even more sensitive than I was [...] I think about what's really important" (P3); and lastly, another linked the pandemic to self-knowledge: "The pandemic helped us to find out a bit more about what our limits are" (P1).

One of the major challenges during the period, having precisely to do with limits, was people's relationship to bereavement. Some participants mentioned experiencing death at the university: "Unfortunately, we lost some colleagues. It's very sad" (P1). In these situations, one participant stated that the university "enacted homages [to deceased colleagues]" (P1). Others referred not only to losses in the professional environment, but also in the family, reflecting the global impact of the pandemic on society.

3.2. Death-related changes in teaching and research resulting from the pandemic

This category gathers together results relating to any changes made by participants in their teaching and research as a result of their experiences during the pandemic. First, the

subcategory titled “Closer teacher-student relationships” is discussed, followed by “The inclusion of death in education research”.

3.2.1. Closer faculty-student relationships

During the pandemic, participants noticed a change in their relationships with students, characterized by greater intimacy and openness. For some, the transition to online teaching not only altered the medium, but also transformed the dynamics of teacher-student interactions. For example, participant P5 recalled that “I had to completely adapt my teaching style, moving from face-to-face to virtual classes. This not only involved using of new digital tools, but also a change in the way I interacted with students”. The perception of invading students’ privacy became evident to others, who expressed concern about intruding in the personal sphere: “Also, there was the feeling that I was invading their private space [...] For me, this view of videoconferencing is really common, but I had the feeling that I was invading part of their home life and that they were a little out of place” (P2). This change in the medium of education led participants to rethink the nature of the teacher-student relationship and created greater sensitivity to the boundaries of personal space in a virtual environment.

Similarly, online teaching provided a platform where students seemed more willing to share their thoughts and emotions. As one participant (P6) remarked, “online classes, although challenging, provided a platform where students seemed more willing to share their thoughts and emotions, perhaps because they felt they were in a safer and more personal space, their own home”. This observation shows that the shift to virtual teaching not only brought technical challenges, but also created an environment that was sometimes conducive to greater emotional openness among partners in the educational process.

In terms of interaction with their colleagues, informants also noted significant shifts, since “The pandemic helped us reassess the relationship between our work and our emotional wellbeing and mental health” (P1). The need to understand the individual circumstances of both colleagues and students became a priority. Flexibility and empathy were highlighted in these new work dynamics: “I think a bit more about the particular situations in the setting, of other people, including my colleagues and my students” (P1). The pandemic served as a catalyst for valuing human relationships in the professional sphere and recognizing the importance of the human factor and the system of personal and professional values. This change in perception underscores the need for a more holistic approach to university teaching, where emotional connection and the wellbeing of all those involved are taken as fundamental principles.

3.2.2. The inclusion of death in educational research

In general, participants stated that to date they had not researched the Pedagogy of Death and did not plan to do so in the near future. This may be due to various factors, such as the cultural taboo surrounding death, the lack of teacher education in this area, and the perception that the subject is alien or irrelevant to certain fields of knowledge. As one (P1) remarked, “It isn’t one of my areas of research [...]. In fact, until we had this interview, I hadn’t thought that research such as yours could be carried out in such a particular context”. The same participant added: “It’s difficult for me to talk about anything related to death because of the subjects I teach. They’re purely technological subjects”. In the same vein, P7 commented that “It isn’t one of my areas of research [...] I’ve never considered it.”

The fact that neither the Pedagogy of Death nor other related topics featured amongst the participants’ lines of research may be due to death being excluded from both the curriculum and teacher education. As P5 indicated, “[We’re not prepared] in terms of infrastructure and teacher education”. These testimonies highlighted the need to address cultural, curricular and educational barriers in order to make death an accepted, normal topic in education research.

3.3. The relevance of the Pedagogy of Death in the light of the pandemic

The last category groups together interviewees' views on the relevance of death as a normal topic in education in the light of the pandemic. First, the subcategory titled "The Pedagogy of Death in university teaching" is discussed, followed by "The Pedagogy of Death in schools".

3.3.1. The Pedagogy of Death in university teaching

Participants' testimonies revealed a need for faculty to be trained in the Pedagogy of Death. Thus, P7 stated: "I think that as teachers we're somewhat lacking in training". This comment underscores the importance of educating teachers, including university teachers, on how to address the topic of death with their students, not only in the context of a pandemic, but also in the face of the numerous loss-related situations that students experience. As P7 commented, "Our students have many [death-related] problems".

With regard to pre-service university teacher education, a need to integrate the Pedagogy of Death into the curriculum was evidenced. One participant (P8) stated: "I support drawing up educational plans on different topics, but at one point I suggested a plan to address the Pedagogy of Death, and the trainees were like, 'What are you talking about, are you mad?' But of course, just as we need to plan how technology will be used in the school, [or] how the library will be used in the school [...], why not a plan to address the Pedagogy of Death?" This comment highlights the importance of including death in the pre-service teacher education curriculum for faculty.

3.3.2. The Pedagogy of Death in schools

In general, participants were in favour of incorporating death as subject-matter in schools, stressing that it is currently taboo: P8 remarked "I think that as a society we avoid all topics related to death, in general terms. Hiding it, concealing it and not dealing with it does us no favours as a society". The same participant added: "It's taboo to talk about death. So we're probably not prepared to deal with the death of a loved one", thereby emphasizing the importance of education and openness in treating death as a normal educational topic.

The social and educational taboo surrounding death is reflected in its absence in curricula; as P1 stated: "It's not included at any stage of education". Regarding its inclusion in curricula and teaching methodology, the importance of cross-curricular and multicultural approaches to education on death from an early age was highlighted: "[Death] is quite cultural and social, and sometimes it also comes out in religious issues" (P1); "I think we should deal with it in some way from childhood or adolescence on" (P5).

4. Discussion

The results of the study afford insights that are of pedagogical interest in all three categories analysed. In relation to experiences during the pandemic (category a), we found that the academic setting, in this case in the field of the education sciences, was not exempt from the challenges of the most critical months of the pandemic. Participants referred to the loss of colleagues and difficulties in coping with death, including on a personal level. These experiences were common to most people in the global crisis caused by the pandemic. Perhaps the most relevant finding, from a pedagogical standpoint, had to do with some comments focusing on personal changes which, given the close relationship between teachers' personal and professional development (Imbernón, 2020), transcended the private sphere and consequently acquired pedagogical and educational significance. Some participants were grateful for "the silence, the peace, and being able to slow down" during the pandemic (P3), or "finding out a bit more about what our limits are" (P1). The study was based on the analysis of personal and professional experiences during the pandemic

and their relationship to the understanding of the Pedagogy of Death among academics who, due to the impact of their publications, are leaders in the education sciences. These testimonies, therefore, are key, since they connect personal experiences with the professional development of university lecturers who educate teachers (Burns et al., 2023). Although these views cannot be generalized to all participants, they suggest that periods of crisis such as the pandemic can be transformed into an opportunity to overcome the personal-professional split in teacher development, including among teacher educators such as the participants in this study. In relation to death, the connection between the personal and teaching or academic practices may make even greater sense, considering its private but also social nature.

These issues perceived by some participants relating to the awareness of vulnerability or silence may be relevant to changes made in teaching and research around death as a result of the pandemic (category b). Thus, some comments pointed to greater intimacy and openness in the pedagogical relationship between faculty and students. Some participants even remarked that online teaching may have something to do with this openness to their feelings. In short, it seems that vulnerability, influenced by the heightened presence of death, can represent a way of opening up to the world (Butler et al., 2016). Universities and their communities were exposed to forms of individual and collective vulnerability that contributed positively to reassessing some fundamental educational values and principles (Ibáñez-Martín and Ahedo, 2023) in order to address pain and suffering. It is worth mentioning here the “compassionate universities” movement, which, although it began before the pandemic (Maratos et al., 2019), later gained momentum as a result of it (Lemon et al., 2023). According to research conducted among students and faculty by Bakelants et al. (2024), a “compassionate university” can be defined as an institution that has clear, transparent, compassionate policies; offers support services for serious illness, death, and bereavement; makes these issues visible through fomenting community awareness; and fosters healthy attitudes towards end-of-life experiences. Compassion can be understood not only in terms of promoting the psychological health of members of the university community, but also, and complementarily, in the context of teacher-student relationships (Andrew et al., 2023), thus strengthening the affective aspects of teaching and learning.

Aside from these testimonies, we did not find that participants had made any changes in their teaching regarding death, nor did they have any particular interest in researching the Pedagogy of Death. In general terms, this line of study was unknown to them, perhaps since the most-cited scholars tend to be engaged on more established lines of research. Although Spain is a leading country in academic production around the Pedagogy of Death (Herrán et al., 2024), the field is still an emerging and relatively unknown line of research.

The third and final category addressed was that of participants' ideas on the relevance of the Pedagogy of Death in the light of the pandemic (category c). Based on their experiences during the pandemic, participants highlighted the importance of educating university teachers in the Pedagogy of Death. Some also emphasized the importance of including it in their pre-service teacher education. The Pedagogy of Death is a field that has barely been explored in university teaching. Although there are studies on university students' education around death in the social sciences (Pitimson, 2021), health (Baykara et al., 2022) and education fields (Rodríguez et al., 2023), we did not find any research or theory in the scholarly literature advocating the comprehensive inclusion of death in university teaching. The “compassionate universities” movement mentioned above is consistent with teaching that takes death and the awareness of finitude into account, and goes beyond the culture of care in situations of pain caused by bereavement or illness. This broader perspective on university teaching, which can be approached through the discipline of university didactics (Zabalza, 2007), defined as the study of general or transdisciplinary processes of teaching and learning, could contribute to the formation of more mature and conscious citizens (Giroux, 2010) with an education affording them greater awareness of death and finitude.

With regard to addressing death in schools, although participants did not pursue this line of research, they were in favour of the incorporation of death as a standard topic in the curriculum. This finding coincides with those of studies into the views of the education community, such as schoolteachers (Rodríguez et al., 2022b), families (Serrano et al., 2024) and students (Rodríguez et al., 2024). Despite this, the curriculum does not include death as subject-matter, nor does it address education on the awareness of death and finitude as a goal, objective, or competence within the framework of what has been termed “holistic education”, as studies in different countries have found (Herrán et al., 2019; Paul et al., 2023; Rodríguez et al., 2022a; Sonbul and Çelik, 2023). This may be due to multiple factors: the taboo on death and topics related to it; the adoption of a competency-based approach to the curriculum; the lack of teacher education; or the resistance to educational and curricular change. Although the general attitude among participants, reinforced by their experiences during the pandemic, was one of openness towards the Pedagogy of Death, we did not find any broad, proactive discourse on why, for what purpose, or how to include death in teaching. Our interpretation of this is that even the most high-profile education scholars also require training on radical topics such as death, which, due to their characteristics, are not normally researched or analysed, although this may seem paradoxical, given their importance for humanity and our education.

5. Conclusions and limitations of the study

At the beginning of the article, we asked ourselves, similarly to Darling-Hammond and Hyler (2020) and Assunção and Craig (2023), whether the pandemic had given rise to new visions of education that might, in this case, include death as a formative element. To answer this question, leading Spanish academics in the education sciences were interviewed based on their number of citations in WoS.

Analysis of the interviews enabled us to draw a number of conclusions. (1) The pandemic had increased the visibility of death, prompting participants to make reflections that could underpin a greater awareness of the educational value of death and finitude. (2) As a result of the pandemic, participants’ relationships with their students had become closer, in terms of understanding and empathy; and this could encourage the development of a Pedagogy of Death also in university teaching, giving rise to more compassionate educational spaces. (3) Participants reported no significant changes in their teaching and research around death, which leads us to the conclusion that, even for leading scholars, further training is required, aimed at integrating the core human topic of death in teaching, student counselling and support and, where appropriate, research. (4) Lastly, participants highlighted the importance of treating death as a standard topic in the curriculum at all stages of schooling.

These conclusions have professional implications for educational change. The first is that we may not yet have analysed sufficiently how education could be reimagined in the wake of the pandemic, integrating it as a radical element of human formation (Herrán, 2020). Hence, it may be of interest to create opportunities for such analysis in the academic context. Secondly, the Pedagogy of Death requires greater political commitment, given the evidence that both the educational community (Rodríguez et al., 2024; Serrano et al., 2024) and academics in the education sciences have called for an education that encompasses death.

This study also has certain limitations that should be mentioned in order to interpret the results and conclusions more rigorously. One of these is that the selection of participants, based mainly on the number of citations in WoS, could be enhanced by including other criteria of academic recognition or impact on educational development. We should also note the bias (potentially positive towards the research topic) that may be inherent in the participation rate of less than 10% of the scholars originally invited. Another is that the research was carried out in the Spanish context; thus, both studies in other countries and

comparative research would be required to broaden the perspectives analysed. Despite this, the study opens up a line of research in the field of the Pedagogy of Death that centres on listening to the voices of those who, in the academic world, conduct research and create educational theory.

Authors contributions

Pablo Rodríguez Herrero. Participation in all phases of the article's development (funding, conceptualisation, theoretical basis, methodology, fieldwork, data analysis, writing, revision).

Agustín de la Herrán Gascón. Participation in all phases of the article's development (funding, conceptualisation, theoretical basis, methodology, fieldwork, data analysis, writing, revision).

Victoria de Miguel Yubero. Participation in the theoretical basis, methodology, data analysis and writing.

Bianca Fiorella Serrano Manzano. Participation in the theoretical basis, methodology, fieldwork, data analysis and writing.

Declaration of AI use:

The authors declare that AI was not used in the preparation of the article.

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